

Personal Income	279,771
Net Savings	26,426
Real Estate	244,313
Other Assets	7,330
Bank Accounts	844,379
Life Insurance	237,657
Individual Savings	563,560
Other Assets	45,000
Investment Account	461,771
Debt	103,700
Net Worth	2,781,981
Resources	4,567,284

How do you measure success? (or do you offer a high-end, high-quality product or a low-cost product?) It's to be both. You should consider on thinking what your customers need you to be. Your logo is the main foundation of your brand. All the promotional materi-

Market Strategy

Marketing strategy goal is to increase sales and achieve advantage over other competitors. It includes short-term and long-term activities of marketing that has to do with the of a company's situation and contribute to its objectives. The objectives will be based on how you gain sales by acquiring and keeping customers. A marketing strategy helps on good messages with the right kind of marketing approaches in order to have a good view of your sales and marketing activities. Putting your strategy into action is how your plan should work. Marketing budgets will be set, at the same time it will also show you you're going to work with your targets, etc.

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Putting your strategy into action is how your marketing plan should work. Marketing budgets will be set, at the same time it will also show you how you're going to work with your targets. It may be through networking, advertising etc. Having the perfect timing with your activities to fit your customers buying cycles will help you saving money and maximizing sales. The marketing plan should be innovative. It should have the details on how your sales are followed up and the activities you doing to develop your offers.

It is a process to allow an organization to focus resources on the greatest opportunities to increase sales and achieve the company's target. Marketing strategy's goal is to increase sales and achieve the advantage over other competitors.

31.86%	30.23%	37.91%
UNIT ITEMS 12 500	UNIT ITEMS 12 500	UNIT ITEMS 12 500
SHIPPING 0.200	SHIPPING 0.200	SHIPPING 0.200
TOTAL 12.700	TOTAL 12.700	TOTAL 12.700

US RATE RISE CHANCES RECEDE AS JOBS GROWTH SLOWS

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ECONOMY OF THE EUROPEAN UNION

WORLD BANK'S STOCK AT ALL-TIME HIGH / US RATE RISE CHANCES RECEDE AS JOBS GROWTH SLOW

WORLD BANK'S STOCK AT ALL-TIME HIGH

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Hand holding a smartphone displaying a news article.

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THE WORLD IS MESSED UP BUT I BELIEVE WE ARE IN A POSITION NOW TO GET IT

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Corruption and globalization:

an overview

Katherine Wilkins¹

Abstract

Despite broad recognition that the transformations of globalization have markedly impacted corruption within and among countries, there remains no clear understanding of where the balance for control of corruption stands today.

This article reviews existing scholarship on how globalization relates to corruption, identifying trends and drawing attention to gaps to be addressed by the contemporary research agenda.

First, this article describes the theoretical model of corruption as interaction between enabling and disabling factors at the international level, beyond the typical unit of analysis of nation-state.

Second, the article offers an overview of empirical findings on how globalization may offer new resources for corruption as well as new constraints. Finally, highlighting critical examinations of the environment in which control of corruption is currently operationalized, this paper calls for attention to state interest in enforcement practices to understand why control of corruption is regarded to be in a difficult position today.

Keywords: Corruption, Globalization, Enforcement, State interest, Cross-border

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1. Introduction

The proliferation of interactions between developed and developing countries we term ‘globalization’ has fundamentally altered our societies, economies, environment, and politics. As a “transformation in spatial organization of social relations and transactions generating transcontinental or inter-regional flows”, globalization complicates how elements of the global ecosystem relate to one another and generates a cascade of new inter-relations (Held et al., 1999, p.438).

Among others, globalization has impacted corruption, both in the form of countries’ patterns and in the exchanges between countries. Economic globalization in particular – the accelerating exchange of capital, services, commodities, and goods worldwide and the associated interdependencies of countries in a global marketplace – not only proliferates opportunities for corruption to occur across borders but also enables systemic patterns within countries by increasing resources (such as development finance) available to existing domestic corruption networks and “[opening] new opportunities for corruption for local elites” (Mungiu-Pippidi, 2019 p.216; Stiglitz, 2003). Contemporary scholarship now recognizes that corruption within countries is often fueled by international inflows (Cooley et al., 2018)

Despite three decades of accumulated research and considerable investment in anti-corruption interventions across the globe, scholars and practitioners alike find the track record sobering: there are very few cases of real success, and many countries are currently stalling or sliding backward. This can in part be explained at the country level – the transition of a society from widespread corruption toward exceptional corruption is complex and time consuming, often with setbacks along the way. But this is far from the full story. Some private companies based in ‘clean’ countries like Denmark and Sweden became drivers of corruption in countries like Brazil and Uzbekistan, while those that promote the anti-corruption agenda internationally – the United States, United Kingdom, and European Union – also serve as prime destinations for the proceeds of corruption occurring elsewhere. These conflicting trends and approaches form the object of a vast literature.

While the global anti-corruption regime continues to develop, the patchwork of multilateral and national tools that currently exist to address the problem continues to face criticism for both not being adequately enforced and for having crucial gaps. Developing strategic approaches to corruption in a globalized world requires both a clear definition of the problem and an evaluation of the types of responses available (Johnsøn 2016). It likewise requires a critical perspective on the operating environment for such responses, as “the investigation, prevention, and prosecution of corruption is profoundly influenced not simply by how corruption is defined, but more deeply, by how we are to understand the character of politics” (Philp, 1997 p.437). That is, the environment in which control of corruption is operationalized, and by whom, matters a great deal.

This article reviews existing scholarship on how globalization relates to corruption, identifying trends and drawing attention to gaps to be addressed by the contemporary research agenda. First, this article describes the theoretical model of corruption as interaction between enabling and disabling factors at the international level, beyond the typical unit of analysis of nation-state. Second, the article offers an overview of empirical findings on both how globalization may offer new resources for corruption as well as new constraints. Finally, highlighting critical examinations of the environment in which control of corruption is currently operationalized, this paper calls for a geopolitical understanding of enforcement practices to fill gaps in understanding why control of corruption is regarded to be in a difficult position today.

2. Control of corruption

Corruption is now more than a concept in scholarly or public discourse. Today, controlling corruption is the subject of considerable public and private investment (through oversight, enforcement, or compliance) as well as a focus of civic activism around the world.

As a “pathology of governance”, corruption is broadly understood in the Aristotelian sense of ‘failure of government to operate in the universal interest, instead serving particularistic interests’ (Mungiu-Pippidi & Fazekas, 2020 p. 13; Mungiu-Pippidi & Hartmann, 2019). Most definitions in use today are some variations on the Nye original, ‘abuse of entrusted public authority for undue private interest’ (see Johnsen, 2016 p.4 for an examination of the strengths and weaknesses of this language). Likewise, ‘endemic’ or ‘systemic’ corruption is distinguished from its more incidental and rare instances – creating a typology of the problem organized by how common it is and by the public level at which it operates (see Heywood, 1997; Rose-Ackerman, 1996).

Operational definitions vary depending on the actors involved and on scale of the activity (see Brown, 2006; Johnston, 2005a for reviews of definitional debates), enabling the concept to be examined in specific contexts.

The literature on causes of corruption at the country level is vast, covering the role of political institutions, economic development, market competition and rents, among other factors (Treisman, 2007). A body of literature considers to how corruption and economic modernization are intertwined, offering a basis for evaluating how global economic integration may impact corruption at the country level. Within this literature, there remains some debate around the role of corruption in early stages of development and at what stage corruption becomes harmful for growth. Bureaucratic corruption has long been theorized to accelerate early economic growth, where “the corruption produced by the expansion of governmental regulation may help stimulate economic development” (Huntington, 2017). This suggests that corruption acts as a “grease” for the early stages of growth, but in later stages becomes “sand” in the gears of economic expansion (Uslaner & Rothstein, 2012). While economic theories offer a strong basis, their explanatory power has been criticized as less able to explain political or systemic corruption (Johnsen, 2016).

This resulted in a paradigm shift away from evaluating corruption at the transactional level and toward hypothesizing about what preconditions and characteristics at the societal level contribute most to its control. This later wave of anti-corruption scholarship stresses the importance of normative constraints on the behavior of both citizens and public officials. That is, “What matters are the rules of the game in a society, as defined by prevailing explicit and implicit behavioral norms” (Rodirk & Subramanian, 2003 p.31). As a result of this theoretical development in the field, we have a wealth of empirical scholarship that confirms the relationship between quality of government, regime type, and control of corruption (see Charron et al., 2014; Johnston, 2005; A. Mungiu-Pippidi & Johnston, 2017; North, D.C., Wallis, J.J., & Weingast, 2009).

In particular, the links between democracy and control of corruption are well documented. A free media², engaged civil society, political agency, electoral accountability, strong rule of law, independent institutions, and an autonomous bureaucracy collectively provide accountability and reduce pathways for privileged interests (Mungiu-Pippidi & Johnston, 2017). The overall societal contextual environment matters a great deal, but scholars also observe that anti-corruption measures fail if ‘principled principals’, that is, well intentioned public officials, are lacking, particularly when corruption is systemic (Persson et al., 2013). Recognizing that principals evaluate potential interest in engaging in a corrupt act not only in terms of monetary benefits versus potential penalties, but also in normative terms such as reputational costs, more recent contributions to this area of theory examine what kinds of reputational costs are significant.

Furthermore, scholars find that ‘club’ dynamics can explain how such reputational costs are framed in decision-making (Dávid-Barrett, 2019; Robert O Keohane & Nye, 2001), emphasizing that scholars should anticipate different types of constraints to be relevant at different levels of inquiry from the society to the industry or firm.

Alina Mungiu-Pippidi has offered a synthetic model summarizing this literature on causes of corruption using the nation-state. This model conceptualizes a continuum with public integrity as the opposite state of corruption, where the balance between enabling and disabling factors determines the state of corruption. This observation provides an elegantly simple image: a balanced scale. In this model, control of corruption occurs when all constraints outweigh all incentives: **Control = Constraints (legal + normative) – Incentives (power discretion + material resources)** (Mungiu-Pippidi, 2011). Delivering equilibrium therefore requires aligning incentive structures on both sides – raising the legal and normative constraints and reducing power discretion and material resources. As introduced in *Europe’s Burden: Promoting Good Governance across Borders*, the processes of globalization offer new resources for and constraints on corruption, and this in turn may require additional considerations for the model beyond what exists discretely within a country, rather applying the logic at the international level. New considerations, including elements such as, on the constraints side, international norm-promotion, and on the resources side, the global offshore system, are introduced and can be visualized in the model below (Mungiu-Pippidi, 2019).

² Among these factors, freedom of the press has the closest correlation with control of corruption (Brunetti & Weder 2003)

The equilibrium model considering globalization

Constraints

Legal: Domestic + International

Anti-money laundering rules;

UN Conventions (UNCAC, UNCTOC); Anti-Bribery rules (FCPA, OECD Anti-Bribery, UK Anti-Bribery); Sanctions; UWOs (UK only); aid conditionalities & suspension

Normative: Local Norms + International Norms + Norm Diffusion

Treaty & multilateral monitoring bodies; Voluntary Initiatives & Business Associations; Social connectivity & broad awareness of corruption; Reputational risks

Resources

Material Resources: Domestic + International

Increased opportunities through trade & foreign investment; Bilateral and development aid funds; Global offshore system; Free flow of finance/capital

Power Discretion: Domestic + International

*New regulatory processes/increased red tape
(Mis)use of international fora*

3. Globalization and (dis)equilibrium

Does globalization have adverse, ambiguous, or beneficial effects for control of corruption within countries?

Answering this question requires unpacking the various dimensions of globalization and how they each offer either additional resources for and/or new constraints on corruption within countries, and then evaluating whether, on balance, the new constraints may counterbalance or outweigh the additional resources.

Globalization increases resources for corruption

Much of our knowledge of cross-border corruption cases come from practitioners. Investigative journalists have exposed individual cross-border corruption schemes and the shocking scale of global money laundering. Watchdog groups monitor misuse of aid resources, and local civil society tracks who receives contracts for development projects in their countries. Scholars and practitioners alike have attempted to measure the true scale and incidence of these flows. Still today, there is no agreed figure for how much of the global economy is directed toward corruption.

Though estimates have circulated in the trillions, these often-cited figures do not appear to be based on any rigorous scholarship (Stephenson, 2016). The United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) estimates that money laundering, of which the proceeds of corruption represent a share, amounts to somewhere between 2-5% of global GDP each year (*Estimating Illicit Financial Flows Resulting from Drug Trafficking and Other Transnational Organized Crimes, 2011*). According to a 2020 report of the Intelligence and Security Committee of Parliament, the value of property in the United Kingdom alone purchased with corrupt funds totals approximately 5 billion British pounds (*Report: Russia, 2020*).

Corruption, similar to other illicit phenomena like organized crime, is bound by the limits of the licit economy and may reflect the restricted opportunities therein (Galeotti, 1995). As the wider world has opened to the corrupt, they have proven entrepreneurial – looking abroad for new markets, deals, facilitation, and safe-haven for their spoils (Cooley & Sharman, 2017).

Such individuals gain access through citizenship-by-investment schemes (‘golden visas’), purchase property in global capitals, and launder their reputations alongside their cash (Bullough, 2018b; Cooley et al., 2018). Corruption networks, like organized crime and terrorist networks, can now “operate transnationally, exploiting loopholes within state-based legal systems to expand their reach” (Shelley, 2011 p.3). At the same time, the global offshore economy provides avenues for corrupt actors to move vast sums out of their countries, stashing it in bank accounts and properties around the world (Bullough, 2018a).

As such, corruption can be thought of as a negative externality of globalization, which generates vast new financial flows among regions and between countries. These inflows, from trade, foreign direct investment (FDI), development and bilateral aid or loans from international finance and development institutions can fuel existing local networks and can help germinate new ones, affecting the “frequency and intensity of localized patterns” of corruption within countries (Rotman, 2001). Scholars have observed that inflows themselves can not only fuel corruption, but also can potentially be comprised of corrupt funds. The IMF found that in 2019, nearly 60% of all foreign direct investment in Russia was made through shell companies – more than any other major economy. Furthermore, IMF research identifies that “a few well-known tax havens host the vast majority of the world’s phantom FDI” citing 10 economies (among them Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Hong Kong SAR, British Virgin Islands, Bermuda, Singapore, the Cayman Islands, Switzerland, Ireland, and Mauritius) as channeling over 85% of such funds (Damgaard et al., 2019).

Research finds that 13% of all FDI between 2005 and 2011 was channeled through Cyprus – making the offshore second only to Great Britain (Ledyaeva et al., 2013). Round-trip investors, nationals who hold funds offshore and re-invest it domestically, “tend to invest in regions with higher levels of corruption, while genuine foreign investors have a strong preference to invest in less corrupt regions” (Ledyaeva et al., 2013).

Among these inflows, bribe payments remain all too common. What determines the rate of occurrence of cross-border bribery cases in each country? Laarni Escresa and Lucio Picci build on empirical knowledge of corruption at the country level, examining the role of economic development, political institutions, among other factors on the incidence of cross-border bribery. Their findings echo empirical evidence on relationship between per capita GDP and corruption at the country level, finding that economic development has a negative effect on corruption. Notably, Escresa and Picci consider relational factors between countries, finding that factors such as cultural proximity have limited effect on corruption beyond that already relevant in the context of bilateral trade (Escresa & Picci, 2020).

Globalization generates new constraints on corruption

Fortunately, while the social, economic, and political changes driven by globalization have both fueled and changed the character of corruption today, they are also generating new possibilities for its control. Anti-corruption theory offers insight into how the many changes driven by globalization are expected to shift the equilibrium model for corruption control, and scholars offer empirical evidence.

Economic constraints

Economic globalization places a range of demands on specific capacities of the administrative state, requiring effective institutions. Theory anticipates that states with autonomous bureaucracies that impartially carry out the business of the state should more easily transfer the gains of economic globalization, but this may not hold beyond economic gains to include social or political gains, and it may not apply when considering equitable gains within a society. Process-tracing the development of control of corruption at the country level reveals a complex relationship between corruption, development, and economic growth (A. Mungiu-Pippidi & Johnston, 2017; Treisman, 2007; Uslaner & Rothstein, 2012). Among the findings in this body of empirical research: institutional demands of managing economic globalization are concentrated on those public services required to ensure market openness, or guarantee transactional integrity, rather than those that enable accountability.

Economic globalization, by removing barriers to international trade and investment, should thereby increase competition across countries, driving down corruption within countries (Krueger, 1974). Indeed, recommendations from global financial institutions for developing countries, especially in the period of post-Cold War integration, were to reduce state protections, anticipating that a free market would offer control of corruption (Stiglitz, 2003; V. Thomas & Nash, 1991). Early empirical findings support this: Ades & Di Tella observe that “corruption is higher in countries where domestic firms are sheltered from foreign competition by natural or policy induced barriers to trade” noting that “almost a third of the corruption gap between Italy and Austria”, as an example, “can be explained by Italy’s lower exposure to foreign competition” (Ades & Di Tella, 1999 p.992). Research emphasizes that it is not merely openness to exchange that is associated with reduced corruption but the quality of exchange. Gokcekus and Knorich (2006) observe that “although an increased level of openness reduces corruption, corruption is reduced even further when the same amount of trade is conducted with a less corrupt trading partner” (Gokcekus & Knörich, 2006 p.191). Globalized transactions introduce considerable information asymmetries, and as such identifying less corrupt trade, investment, and operational partners is a challenge. The detrimental consequences of information asymmetries on capital flows have been confirmed empirically (see Javorcik & Wei, 2009 for an overview). As a result, policies that would facilitate better transactions have begun to be introduced, such as know-your-customer rules and beneficial ownership transparency. But not only are such policies absent from all but a few countries, they are rarely robust enough to be effective (such as

requiring beneficial ownership registries to be made public). Counter-intuitively, these constraints also do not appear to be working as expected. The Global Shell Games study found that shell company formation firms based in non-tax havens were more likely to ignore know-your-customer rules than those based in identified tax havens (Findley et al., 2014).

Appetite to attract FDI could potentially be a strong motivation for countries to undertake anti-corruption reforms. Already in 1995 it was empirically demonstrated that corruption is negatively associated with private investment and overall growth (Mauro, 1995). In fact, the link between wealth and corruption within countries is well explored – poor countries tend to have higher corruption levels (La Porta et al., 1999; Triesman, 2000). Further inquiries provide evidence for the link between corruption and reduced growth (Careaga & Weingast, 2003; Knack & Keefer, 1995; Rodrik et al., 2004). Perceived widespread corruption in a country can result in reduced foreign direct investment, removing resources for economic growth (Lambsdorff, 2013; Lambsdorff & Cornelius, 2000). Today nearly every international credit rating system or business index, such as Standard & Poor’s Sovereign Debt Risk ratings or the World Bank’s Doing Business report, take topics like public budget transparency and rule of law in business transactions into account³. Uzbekistan, for example, after decades of opacity under Islam Karimov announced that it would begin opening basic economic data and adopting global accounting standards to be rated by the major credit agencies and attract FDI. There is an important caveat to these findings, however: petty corruption is more likely to deter foreign investors than grand corruption (Lambsdorff, 2005).

³ We also observe that such indices are not always reliable and in fact themselves be subject to corrupt manipulation, as evidenced by the scandal that saw the cancellation of the World Bank’s doing business report

Note that the measures needed to attract FDI (and thus their constraining effect) only apply to this narrow area of transparency and institutions needed for business to operate, while grand corruption is largely left unchecked by this constraint. Additionally, firms are observed to not proactively anticipate corruption risks, but rather follow a reactive approach once corruption issues arise (Hauser & Hogenacker, 2014).

In contrast, loans and development aid from international finance and development institutions can offer powerful incentives for countries to make concrete changes on issues such as transparency and rule of law. Anti-corruption principles have become mainstreamed into the conditionalities often imposed for development financing. However, loans are often given on the basis that efforts will be made rather than that the conditions must first be met, and so the constraining effect is attenuated. In practice, many reforms are made on paper but not all translate into reality. Development projects, such as those funded by the World Bank or bilateral donors, face the same transactional risks as trade and FDI. As a result, financial inflows can reinforce existing corruption networks by funding subsidiaries ultimately owned by public officials. Systematic evaluation quantifying this is lacking but anecdotal evidence from individual countries abounds, often from practitioners. Examining development aid to Honduras, research underscored that domestic corruption networks, despite well-meaning due diligence, can be strengthened by aid flows and become “integrated with transnational kleptocratic networks” (Chayes, 2017). Economists like Joseph Stiglitz have also emphasized that such programs, no matter how well intentioned, can effectively subsidize corruption in the destination country (Stiglitz, 2003). The Pandora Papers revealed that while Canada sent hundreds of millions in foreign aid to Jordan, facing an acute water crisis among other pressures, the King of Jordan acquired 14 properties abroad through 36 shell companies (Fitzgibbon, 2021). Given that Jordan is a strategic partner for Canada in the region, there may be political incentives for not withdrawing aid despite these negative impacts.

Legal & policy constraints

Scholars have hypothesized that countries with a higher degree of globalization may have lower incidence of corruption because “globalization makes countries subject to international norms and rules”. (Koyuncu & Ünver, 2017). It is remarkable to consider just how relatively new anti-corruption as clearly defined good governance standard is within international rules, and how quickly this concept has spread globally beyond its original promoters. The initial articulation of anti-corruption as a rule is presented in 1977 with the passage of the US Foreign Corrupt Practices Act (FCPA) criminalizing the act of bribery for US firms operating abroad, and later, for all firms even loosely connected to US financial markets.

By 2000, rules formalize globally, including through the 1997 OECD Anti-Bribery Convention and the adoption of the United Nations Convention against Corruption in 2003. Enforcement however followed much later, not regularly in practice until the late 1990s (in some European countries, companies could deduct bribes from tax filings as a business expense until 1998) and only sharply increased in the last 20 years. Before this, US industry argued that the FCPA disadvantaged American companies in an increasingly globalized market (George, B.C., Lacey, K.A. & Birmele, J. 2000).

In fact, the FCPA was ‘strategically under-enforced’ until other developed economies were bound by similar rules under the 1997 OECD Anti-Bribery Convention. (Brewster, 2017). If economic arguments drove initial under-enforcement, today the comparatively higher rate is often linked to broader agendas such as democratic norms, national security, and human rights. Alongside the fundamental legal framework, we have the articulation of anti-money laundering rules and an additional range of still-developing policy instruments including know-your-customer rules, beneficial ownership transparency, or bans in some jurisdictions on all-cash real estate purchases (‘Geographic Targeting Orders’ in the United States). These policy instruments, far from universal, are present in only a few countries, and in general are still under development.

Difficulties in developing legal and policy constraints that not only are fit to purpose but can adequately reach the problem are exacerbated by the globalized context. Globalization is as much a political transformation, ‘breaking the exclusive link between geography and political power’, as it is an economic and technological one (D. Held & McGrew, 2000 p. 11). Scholars emphasize that “sovereignty is no longer a sanctuary for states. In effect, globalization has decreased the ability to control what crosses borders in either direction” (Brown, S. S., & Hermann, 2002 p. 32). As Johnston points out, the fact that corruption schemes bridge various jurisdictions problematizes accountability (Johnston, 1998). Such jurisdictional limitations have meant home-country regulations cannot completely ‘reach’ global corruption issues (P. Nichols, 1999). As a result, states cannot tackle globalized corruption alone. Globalization necessitates a view of states and of societies not as autonomous, self-contained entities but rather as actors within a global ecosystem comprised not just of other states, but also of multinationals and non-state actors.

As the domain of the state is diminished relative to other actors, states are incentivized to partner with non-state actors, most visibly private firms or non-governmental organizations (NGOs) (Cooley, 2003). In this dynamic environment, the distribution of resources and relative agency among actors is not static and continues to shift. This has been a boon for the field in many ways: local civil society organizations may have more nuanced information about local corruption patterns and networks and their participation in enforcement efforts offer validity and legitimacy to the processes.

Scholars point to some limitations in the legal and policy constraints we have today. The development of the global anti-corruption regime, that is, all the legal and policy instruments created by countries to control for corruption occurring between and among countries was heavily influenced by anti-corruption theories prevailing at the time and remains in some ways hobbled by this initial impetus. The domination of an economic understanding of corruption meant that the framework arose around creating accountability for corruption at the transactional level, chiefly bribery (Hopkin, 2002). Enforcement remains concentrated on this rather than on, for example, identifying, seizing, and returning all the proceeds of corruption currently held in the west, although this effort is growing. There are thus broader debates in the field about how the regime is delivering accountability. Who (legal or natural persons) is held accountable, who receives redress, and who escapes accountability? While ‘accountability’ is a term regularly used in discussions of global governance, there is “little agreement on whether accountability takes an analogous form between national and transnational domains, and thus whether the transnational extension of the concept overstretches the term – blurring or distorting our analysis of meanings and purpose” (Macdonald, 2015).

These tensions are visible in the normative contestation that continues for topics such as conditionality for asset return. Not only who is held accountable, but how violators of rules are held to account is a crucial element in constraining corrupt behavior (Mookherjee, D., & Png, 1995). The legal-technical interventions often constrain corruption by chasing it on a case-by-case basis, rather than pushing for systemic changes that prevent such cases in the first place. As a result, among contemporary anti-corruption scholars, there is a growing paradigm against legal-technical interventions in favor of explicitly political or normative approaches (Lohaus & Gutterman, 2021).

Normative constraints

Governments, international organizations, and advocacy groups alike increasingly verbalize control of corruption in normative terms. Scholars find that emerging norms around anti-corruption and social good drive multilateral cooperation, in contrast to economic interests (Windsor & Getz, 2000). The shift toward a norm-centered approach is one example of how “globalization will affect governance processes and be affected by them” (Keohane et al., 2002 p. 193). States have an interest in norm promotion – establishing instruments according to a normative paradigm is one way in which states can reach actors in global processes outside their exclusive domain. As such, there is a political dimension to norm promotion, such as is visible in modern-day initiatives like the U.S. Summit for Democracy, or in the language used in bilateral relations. Normative alignment can assist in brokering and maintaining collective action initiatives (Thomas et al., 2009). Gradual normative alignment is also potentially beneficial in that it offers a counterbalance to the competitive forces of economic interest and can accelerate alignment of practices in mutual, rather than individual, interest.

As the global diffusion of ideas has led to wide recognition that corruption is antithetical to the development of healthy societies (Robertston, 1992), and as people have far greater access to information, public demand for good governance has increased.

The development of the elements of democratic society are all independently correlated with control of corruption. Reducing corruption not only improves state effectiveness, it is now intertwined with public legitimacy (Marquette, 2011). Anti-corruption is now a common instigating force behind the majority of political transitions not due to electoral cycles or death (Chayes, 2016). Attitudes toward corruption, however, are not solely driven by importing external norms. Nichols, for example, finds that perceptions of corruption in relatively-isolated Kazakhstan match well with global standards (Nichols, 2001).

Rather, they reflect the result of an increasingly interconnected world, the arrival of e-citizens with access to mobilizing technology and informational tools (such as international media or reports from global watchdog organizations not regularly available in a country) that can give both a target to demands and a means to realize them. By contrast, for countries that respond negatively to social globalization, such as by censoring content available online, there appears to be some impact on anti-corruption norm integration, perhaps by reduced social demand. In this view, the country becomes a “selective filter and modifier” for what arrives via a global network (Keohane et al., 2000 p.199).

Rothstein (2009) finds that ‘windows of opportunity’ for reform follow ‘big bang’ whole-of-society changes such as major political transitions. These transitions within states do not happen in a vacuum, and anti-corruption interventions often feature prominently in the agendas of international organizations or bilateral donors who may offer resources. Research emphasizes how competitive transitional environments can be, and how necessary that structural changes (such as to the judiciary) are to promote development toward control of corruption. This echoes what we know about corruption and democracy more generally: in the initial stages of democratic development, corruption rises (as new opportunities for rent-seeking emerge through transfer of power via elections, ‘competitive particularism’), then precipitously fall as democracy consolidates (Acemoglu & Robinson, 2012; North, D.C., Wallis, J.J., & Weingast, 2009; Rodrik et al., 2004). Triesman (2007) notes it is not merely a country’s level of democracy that is associated with control of corruption but rather the number of years it has been a democracy, suggesting that normative constraints may arise from the embedding of democratic practice. This finding is echoed in lessons learned from country-level approaches, particularly in the concept of ‘deep democratization’ from below as critical to controlling corruption (Johnston, 2005 ch.8, 2014). What remains still somewhat underexplored is the tension between promotion from below or inside and promotion from above or outside.

What do we know about the (im)balance in control of corruption?

In the context of globalization, scholars find that economic connectivity is not only not a panacea for growth, but it can also exacerbate localized corruption issues. Scholars fail to observe cross-country convergence in per capita GDP— an expected result of the “catching up” process in economic integration – identifying weak governance as the primary reason for this finding (Chowdhury, 2004, 2005). As demonstrated through empirical studies, as countries integrate into a global economy, corruption can not only be a barrier to growth and translating the gains of economic globalization into human development, but in some cases increased international economic connectivity can fuel domestic corruption.

Ades and Di Tella (1999) observe that both market structure and the level of rent possibilities in general are determining factors for levels of corruption observed. Beesley identifies that economic openness can have perverse effects when rent possibilities are high, in fact fueling bureaucratic corruption (Beesley, 2015).

Likewise, what stage of economic development a country is in as it participates in the global economy predicts whether connectivity is positively or negatively associated with control of corruption. Examining whether countries that exhibit a high degree of economic globalization also show a lower degree of corruption compared to countries that are less open, an investigation examining cross-sectional data for 127 countries finds a linear relationship between globalization and reduced corruption only for high- and middle-income countries, with no significant impact observed for low-income countries (Lalountas et al., 2011). Responding to the Lalountas study by considering the African context, Asongu found that it is the political and social dimensions of globalization that are significantly associated with control of corruption in high- and middle-income countries (Asongu, 2014).

By contrast, in countries with low per capita income where the economic dimension of global integration is more pronounced, the effects of globalization on control of corruption are limited. This important finding aligns with what modernization theory anticipates: that high corruption levels are likely to be observed at early stages of economic growth. It also directly challenges assumptions that market improvements alone arising out of economic connectivity can generate benefits for corruption control in the absence of domestic good governance constraints. And finally, it points to the relative higher importance of social and political constraints.

Does globalization drive a vicious cycle or a virtuous circle?

Controlling corruption to the degree it becomes exceptional and rare is the result of a long process of development. Globalization, too, describes a process along a continuum from isolation toward connectivity. It is thus worth examining corruption and globalization in terms of how these trajectories align and if scholars anticipate threshold conditions to influence the relationship. Already, scholarship on control of corruption identifies certain benchmarks and inflection points. Applying models from modernization theory, scholars identify certain ‘doorstep’ conditions that precede ‘tipping points’ on the path to control of corruption (Lipset, n.d.; North, D.C., Wallis, J.J., & Weingast, 2009).

The process of globalization has analogues: ‘doorstep conditions’ such as a certain degree of institutional development or social connectivity and ‘tipping points’ such as signing of trade agreements or joining multilateral initiatives. While this remains an underexplored area, Attila (2013) offers insight, finding that not all developing countries gain from globalization “unless they participate more intensively in the globalization process and move beyond a critical threshold” (Attila, 2013 p. 541). Pinpointing threshold conditions in globalization for control of corruption would be significant for understanding what conditions are more likely to tilt the balance toward control in certain contexts, especially given the observed differences between developed and developing countries.

Has globalization fueled some kinds of corruption, while reducing others?

Given that globalization seems to fuel corruption of various kinds, are some manifestations particularly affected by globalization, and if so, what significance does that have for society? The distinct impacts of different manifestations of corruption are well explored. Some forms of corruption, such as ‘petty’ bribery, are directly experienced by the public in daily life and disproportionately affect the most vulnerable, especially when it is widespread in areas like healthcare, basic public services, and education, having the effect of denial of services to those who cannot afford to pay bribes (Alesina & Angeletos, 2005; Chetwynd et al., 2003).

Some scholars argue that petty corruption, while conceptually distinct from political or grand corruption, serves to reinforce a problematic status quo and raise overall tolerance for corrupt behavior (O'Brien, 2020). Others underscore that the term 'petty' is misleading, minimizing the devastating effects that corruption in public service can have on societies (Bohórquez, E., & Devrim, 2012). Political or grand corruption, in contrast, involves high level officials and vast sums. While citizens do not directly experience the transactions that constitute political or grand corruption, they most certainly feel its effects: these forms of corruption harm in the aggregate by creating extreme market distortions or siphoning public funds for elite enrichment, ultimately resulting in the impoverishment of public services and sluggish development. Grand corruption is also more likely to be connected to certain negative behaviors associated with power-preservation, such as institutional political capture, or restrictions on watchdog activity. In this way, it also harms in the specific: corrupt elites have silenced through intimidation or lawsuits (so called 'SLAPP suits'), administratively harassed, jailed, and killed those working to expose their crimes (C. Bjørnskov & Freytag, 2016; Christian Bjørnskov et al., 2018). It is this type that has been more often linked to the processes of globalization.

Globalization tilts the balance toward more resources for grand corruption, both through the reinforcement of domestic rent markets where public officials maintain monopoly control and through the subsequent allowance for vast offshoring of their wealth. However, the legal and policy constraints created by or enhanced by globalization are less likely to address issues of grand corruption than they are petty or transactional corruption.

With respect to these observations, there is current scholarly debate about the orientation of the existing enforcement framework for corruption globally. Scholars observe that the global enforcement system has grown "in the absence of formal process or reasoned articulation" (Westbrook, 2011). As a result, "the liability framework for engaging in transnational corruption has almost exclusively been the result of political expediency rather than empirical information" (Obidairo, 2011). Recent scholarship argues the transactional focus of the global enforcement regime comes at the expense of reforming the rules of the international economic system or tackling the networked aspects of corruption (Katzarova, 2019). These arguments may help explain why the constraints we have in place today, while we can point toward positive effects, have not effectively managed to demonstrably reduce political or grand corruption. Indeed, the political corruption that is linked to backsliding in democratic norms (the very same norms that also contribute to reigning in petty corruption) within countries appears to be going unchecked, fueling a potential vicious cycle.

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Photo by Christian Dubovan.

4. Conclusions and further questions

As described, the relationship between globalization and corruption occurs across economic, political, and social dimensions and along a continuum of the local, national, regional, and international levels.

At this moment, anti-corruption scholarship has a better grasp of how the political, social, and economic dimensions of globalization impact control of corruption individually and which dimensions are most significant in what contexts than it does how these dimensions interrelate. Thanks to the work of practitioners and scholars, we know, in principle, how to control corruption globally.

While we can point to areas where constraints on globalized corruption are lacking or are too weak, there is less conclusive evidence on where the overall balance stands compared to ten years ago. In part, that is due to serious gaps in data availability – we simply do not know conclusively, for example, the overall amount of global trade that is compromised by corruption or the total amount of ill-gotten gains from one country held by another. But there is no doubt that these issues are persistent and that their scale is substantial. Beyond this, one explanatory factor for why global enforcement seems to not be effective is that in its efforts identify and promote constraints, the anti-corruption field has had somewhat lesser focus on the power and politics behind enforcement. An examination of the imbalance in enforcement is needed that accounts for choices states make to or not to adopt enforcement tools and to use them.

A critical view on the existing imbalance in control of corruption

Is it not a lack of technical knowledge on how to control for corruption that hampers progress but rather a failure of political will? Globalization places multiple, at times conflicting or incompatible, demands on states for how to address the issue of corruption. The global governance regime for corruption can be described as ‘loosely coupled spheres of authority’ where the legal and policy frameworks in different countries must either coordinate or compete (Zurn, 2018). Development and implementation of a global enforcement regime is thus not a politically neutral process. Empirical evidence demonstrates that states make rational choices to enforce or not enforce existing rules, to pursue technical reforms, and in their relationships with non-state actors. While the rules of the global anti-corruption enforcement system are set and enforced by states, states can also be spoilers to this system. And, while the assumption might be that only highly corrupt countries obstruct efforts to address gaps in enforcement, experience would show this is not the case: even champions of the anti-corruption agenda can obstruct developments when it is not in their interest.

Concerns about how enforcement advantages or disadvantages states in a competitive global arena not only shaped the development of the anti-corruption regime but continues to shape policy choices. Increasingly, recent actions by the world's main enforcing countries put anti-corruption efforts in foreign policy terms. The entanglement of anti-corruption efforts with broader strategic policy may mean that it is national security interests or political competition, rather than normative goals, that spur the adoption and use of anti-corruption instruments. States may also face tough choices when it comes to new measures that would increase constraints on foreign policy partners, and corruption issues may drive insecurity in relations among states. How states manage corruption issues in their diplomatic relations, through coordination or competition, has received little attention.

This gap in the literature means we cannot yet account for why enforcement, apart from US anti-bribery actions, is reported to be generally stalling and why adoption of anti-corruption rules even in countries that have led the agenda remains so contentious. Existing research in the field on anti-bribery does point to the possibility that states, as rational actors, are more motivated by normative factors now than they were three decades ago, when economic interest drove enforcement. Confirmation of this shift in motivations for other types of enforcement instruments such as beneficial ownership transparency or the use of sanctions could inform how cooperation can be reinforced. A better understanding of how choices are made could offer insight both for strengthening multilateral cooperation and to inform the policy agenda of countries championing anti-corruption enforcement.

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